

PREFERRED COMMUNITY-BASED LEARNING STRATEGY: PREDICTING SCIENTIFIC COMPETENCIES AND NATURAL DISASTER MANAGEMENT SOFT SKILLS OF GRADE 8 DISTANCE LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Recent trends in education tell us that learning should be in the context of community. The purpose of this study was to predict the scientific competencies and natural disaster management soft skills through the preferred community-based learning strategy of Grade 8 distance learners at San Pablo City Integrated High School for the school year 2020-2021. The study employed descriptive research design. The researcher opted to use descriptive survey method to determine if the preferred community-based learning strategy of the respondent was significantly related to scientific competencies and natural disaster management soft skills of the learners. The salient findings of the study were as follows: The preferred community-based learning strategy of the respondents was the work-based learning/education. Though all community-based learning strategies fall on the “true of me” interpretation, the findings revealed that learners preferred learning strategy that has a link with their future work. Furthermore, the test scores result in the achievement test also show that supplemental activities play an important role in distance learning modality. Conversely, the level of disaster management soft skills of the learners was in the “Highly skilled” category. This showed that the respondents were equipped with interpersonal and cognitive skills that can be used in times of disaster. Based on these, the following conclusions were drawn: There is a significant relationship between the preferred community-based learning strategy and the learner’s scientific competencies and natural disaster soft skills with the p-values of less than 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance suggesting the positive correlation between variables. Preferred community-based learning strategy significantly predicted learners’ scientific competencies. On the other hand, work-based learning strategies such as cooperative programs significantly predicted natural disaster management soft skills of the respondents while internship predicted cognitive skills with the p-value less than 0.01 level of significance reinforcing the positive correlations among variables.

Keywords: community-based learning strategy, scientific competency, natural disaster management soft skills, distance learning, descriptive research, San Pablo City, Laguna Philippines